

D. 7.6 – PROGRAMME AND SUMMARY/OUTLINE OF THE PROJECT ADVANCEMENTS AND DECISIONS TAKEN AT THE 2ND STEERING COMMITTEE MEETING

WP7 – Management and Coordination

Contributors

Lucio Pisacane, IRPPS–CNR
Nicolò Marchesini, IRPPS–CNR
Serena Tagliacozzo, IRPPS–CNR
Marco Cellini, IRPPS–CNR
Cristiana Crescimbene, IRPPS–CNR
ALL PARTNERS

Reviewers

Cristiana Crescimbene, IRPPS–CNR

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

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<i>Project Full Title</i>	gEneSys - Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems
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1. INTRODUCTION: THE PROJECT GENESYS AND ITS TIMELINE

Led by the National Research Council of Italy, Institute for Research on Population and Social Policies (CNR-IRPPS), the project **gEneSys (Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems)** aims to contribute to equal participation of women and men in the energy sector and to mainstream the SDG5 goals (concerning gender equality) into the SDG7 goals. With this goal in mind, the project envisages research activities to better understand the relationships between gender and energy transition/transformation in the extant scientific knowledge and knowledge communities (WP1) and to interrogate this relationships through ad-hoc designed surveys to knowledgeable actors ("actors of change") as well as to lay citizens ("recipients of change") (WP1 and WP2). The project acknowledges the relevance of international cooperation with African partners for the realization of a fair and just energy transition dedicating an entire WP (WP4) to identifying the needs and opportunities in Africa to advance women in energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders. Moreover, the project plans for practical activities to mainstream the project's key themes into the students' and teachers' training and curricula (WP3). Finally, the project seeks to pave the way for a sustainable impact by the development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions (WP5).

The project started officially on February 1st, 2023. In line with the project timeline, the kickoff meeting was organized at the beginning of M2 (on March 7th and 8th) summoning the representatives from all partner organisations. The kick-off marked the opportunity to lay out a plan for the activities to be carried out in the following three years and co-define rules for effective collaborations within the consortium (for more details see D7.1). During the meeting, one of the decisions taken was to hold a second project meeting six months after, in October 2023, at the Franhoufer IAO premises in Berlin. The decision to hold the second steering committee meeting in a relatively short timeframe was guided by the need to (i) monitoring whether the activities commenced without significant bottlenecks; (ii) closely overseeing the planning of the activities of the second year the project during which many tasks are to be performed; (iii) discussing opportunities for dissemination and outreach in view of the rapid generation of new data in the first and second year of the project.

In the months that followed the kick-off meeting, the research-related activities envisaged in WP1 started with the performance of a systematic literature review and of a comprehensive ontology of the energy transition domain. These activities, reported in D1.1, allowed to set the basis for a common understanding of the energy-gender nexus and helped partners to navigate through the available evidences.

Thus, at the time of the second project meeting, terminologies and dimensions of the gender-energy nexus were consolidated and jointly agreed upon.

2. THE SECOND PROJECT MEETING IN BERLIN

The second project meeting (see annex 1 and 2 for the full agenda and list of participants) took place in Berlin on 23rd and 24th October (one full day and one half day) and sought to achieve the following objectives.

- (i) Set out a plan and establish collaborations for the upcoming tasks.
- (ii) Take stock of the work performed since the onset of the project and identify gaps or unaddressed aspects;
- (iii) Discuss together the results of the first M&E survey;
- (iv) Discuss opportunities for internal and external collaborations and dissemination of results.

As for point (i), the coordinator asked the leaders of the tasks whose start was impending, to prepare a power point presentation to describe 1) the workplan of the task and its proposed timeline 2) the inputs requested from other partners and, 3) the relation between the tasks and the other WPs (e.g. whether the task required feeds from other WPs). A list of these presentations is available in the annex 3.

Regarding point (ii), the CNR and ENEA team, respectively leading T1.1 and T1.2 had the chance to present the work performed in the systematic literature review of the gender-energy nexus and in the ontology of the energy systems. Results were jointly discussed and suggestions were added to the final version of the D1.1.

In terms of point (iii), one of the key tenet of the gEneSys consortium, as established in the kick off meeting and articulated in D7.1., was the creation of a working climate based on collaborative and mutual respect values, whereby the competencies of all the members (including senior and junior staff) are acknowledged and appreciated. In this respect, it was deemed crucial to understand and possibly resolve bottlenecks that could prevent the smooth collaboration among partner organisations as well as the individual partner organisations' full involvement in the project activities. For this reason, a M&E strategy was set out (see D.7.3) to gather information, in addition to the timely and effective performance of the tasks, on indicators related to the relational dynamics playing out within and externally to the consortium. As part of this strategy, a survey was sent to all partners few weeks prior to the Berlin meeting and results were discussed in a dedicated section of the meeting (see annex for the presentation of the M&E survey results).

Regarding point (iv), the WP6 leader presented the collaborations forged since the onset of the project and possible venues for project's activities and results dissemination and for extending outreach. Opportunities for dissemination identified included the European Renewable Energy Week, the Gender Summit and collaborations with sister projects. In terms of scientific outlets, the consortium considered the possibility to publish T1.1 and T1.2's results in energy-related journals (e.g. *Energy Research and Social Science*) and to reach out to journals' editors to

propose a Special Issue tackling gender-energy nexus (in particular Interdisciplinary Science Reviews by Taylor and Francis).

Finally, the meeting was also the opportunity to officially introduce to the consortium two early career researchers hired by CNR as part of the gEneSys coordination team and to present the results of the project led by Empirica on the gender imbalances in the energy-related workforce (results are now officially available on the EC website https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/news/all-research-and-innovation-news/gender-balance-ri-field-improve-role-women-energy-transition-2024-03-08_en)

3. KEY DECISIONS TAKEN

At the end of the meeting, the team agreed on the following decisions/list of actions:

1. Next steering committee meeting will be hosted by Jagiellonian University in Krakow in June 2024
2. Explore opportunities for dissemination including the European Renewable Energy Week, the Gender Summit and collaborations with sister projects.
3. Scientific outlets to publish results in energy-related journals (e.g. *Energy Research and Social Science*) and to reach out to journals' editors to propose a Special Issue tackling gender-energy nexus (in particular Interdisciplinary Science Reviews by Taylor and Francis).
4. Plan the future project activities following a shared tasks distribution accordingly to the WP ppt presentation.

4. WAY FORWARD

On the short term, the gEneSys meeting sets the start of a number of activities that were planned ahead in 2024. A common task plan was drafted and shared with partners to coordinate the project activities.

5. ANNEX

5.1. ANNEX 1: List of attendees to the project kickoff meeting

GeneSys Project Meeting – 24.-25.10.23, CERRI, Berlin

ID	Name	Signature
1	Sabine Loos	
2	Nana Ama Browne KLUTSE	online!
3	Gill ALLWOOD	online!
4	Raphael Heffron	online!
5	Rocio Diaz-Chavez	Rocio Diaz Chavez
6	Yara Evans	Yara Evans
7	Lucio Pisacane	Lucio Pisacane
8	Serena Tagliacozzo	Serena Tagliacozzo
9	Marco Cellini	Marco Cellini
10	Martina Rogato	absent!
11	Elizabeth Pollitzer	E Pollitzer
12	Vassillo CHIAEA	Vassillo
13	Aleksandra Wagner	Aleksandra Wagner
14	Antonio De Nicola	Antonio De Nicola
15	Gregorio D'Agostino	Gregorio D'Agostino
16	Cloe Mirenda	Cloe Mirenda
17	Dr. Clemens Striebing	

20. Clara PERSOCCI

18 VITTORIA PERI (IT) Vittoria Maria Peri

19 Dr. Ann Saucier

5.2. ANNEX 2: Project Meeting Full Agenda

gEneSys - Project Meeting - Agenda

October, 24th and 25th 2023

Fraunhofer IAO CeRRI, Hardenbergstraße 20 - Berlin

October 24th

Fraunhofer IAO CeRRI - Hardenbergstraße 20

8:45	Registration and welcome coffee
9:00:	gEneSys lifecycle: where we stand and where we go - CNR coordination team
09:15	WP1 – T1.3 Gendered assessment of energy-systems-knowledge-community – ENEA (20 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
09:45	WP1 – T1.4 – Gendered assessment of EU policies for sustainable energy systems - CNR (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
10:10	WP1 – T1.5 – Gendered assessment of stakeholder organisations in sustainable energy systems - CNR (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
10:35	Coffee break
11:00	Getting to know the three invited advisory board members
11:15	WP2 – T2.1 Exploring intersectional power-gender relations – IAO CeRRI (20 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
11:45	WP3 – T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among pre-school and school age students – UJ (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
12:10	WP3 – T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems – UJ (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
12:40	Lunch break
14:15	WP4 – T4.1 Review the past and still active research and innovation cooperation programmes – AIMS (20 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
14:45	WP5 – T5.1 Identification of criteria for the selection of a model pathway – IC (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
15:10	WP5 – T5.2 Integrating gender perspectives into Energy SHIFTS – IC (15 minutes), Partner feedback and synergies (10 minutes)
15:35	Preliminary results from WP1- SLR, Grey Literature review and Energy system ontology – CNR ENEA UJ and all partners (25 minutes)

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16.00	Synergy and partners collaboration toward publication of results and policy tools – (45 minutes) all partners
16:45	Afternoon snack and end of works
19:00	Social Dinner, Schleusenkrug Müller-Breslau-Str. 14b 10623 Berlin

October 25TH

Fraunhofer IAO CeRRI - Hardenbergstraße 20

09:30	WP6 – PORTIA – Communication and Dissemination (30 minutes), Q&A (10 minutes)
10:10	Presentation by sister CINEA project Gender Balance in the R&I Sector – Karsten Gareis Empirica (15 minutes, on line)
10:25	Coffee break
11:00	WP7 – Management and coordination – CNR (30 minutes), Q&A (15 minutes)
11:30	Synergy and partners collaboration toward publication of results and policy tools – (45 minutes) all partners
12.15	Light Lunch
13.30	AOB and bilateral meetings – all partners, where relevant (60 minutes)

5.3. ANNEX 3: gEneSys KOM power point presentations on future activities

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

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SNA: Number of papers

- Number of papers written by a researcher

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SNA: Authority

- Authority measures to what extent the topics in an author's papers influence the topics in his/her coauthors' papers

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SNA: Neighbour susceptibility

- The neighbour susceptibility index measures to what extent the topics in an author's papers are influenced by the topics in his/her coauthors' papers

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SNA: Novelty

- Novelty measures the ability of a researcher to produce work that is both novel (i.e., original, unexpected) and appropriate (i.e., useful adaptive concerning task constraints).
- It is given by the number of times he/she has been the one that introduced a topic for the first time

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Statistical significance

- For each indicator, we ask if the achieved results are statistically significant
- In the example, the yellow curve represents the distribution of randomly selected groups of the same size as the women in the considered community

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Framework for gendered assessment

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T1.3 Deadlines

- 15/12/2023. End data analysis
- 15/1/2024. Results interpretation
- 1/2/2024. Draft of D1.2
- 1/3/2024. Release of D1.2

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T1.3 Participants

AIMS ...

CNR: Cice Miranda, Chiara Vassillo, Marco Cellini, Daniela Luzi, Fabrizio Rboraro,

ENEA: Antonio De Nicola, Gregorio D'Agostino, Tatiana Patriarca, Maria Guarglia Migliore

FRAUNHOFER ...

IC ...

UI ...

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Explored dimensions

The survey aim to gauge employees' overall job satisfaction and assess the organisational culture, work-related quality of life and collaboration dynamics. Building on **CNEA survey results** the questionnaire will include questions on:

- gender inequalities and strategies to tackle them along
- workers' perspectives to support the development of the sector in the future.

Coverage: The survey will be distributed in Italy, Germany, Poland and United Kingdom + the African Institute for Mathematical Sciences network in Africa

Distribution: EU survey/Time survey link through national networks of target organizations

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Mapping target organization - Italy

8 categories of stakeholders

- Companies involved in the energy sector;
- Supranational institutions operating in the country;
- National institutions;
- Association (also trade associations);
- Authorities Regulatory bodies;
- Media;
- Environmental organization;
- Academia (University, Centre and Research Institution).

Within these 8 categories, we have identified a total of 226 individuals who will be contacted shortly to participate in the questionnaire.

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Partners contribution

- Review the questionnaire structure and questions
- Testing the questionnaire with two experts in depth interview in the respective countries (Italy, Poland, Germany, UK+AIMS)
- Mapping your own countries potential target organisations
- Spreading out the survey link in your country

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Timeline

- Questionnaire ready for your review (end of October)
- Testing the questionnaire with two experts through in-depth interview in the respective countries (Italy, Poland, Germany, UK+AIMS) (one month-end of November)
- Mapping your own countries potential target organisations (two month-end of November)
- Spreading out the survey link in your country (December/January)

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WP II
Exploring gendered intersectional patterns in citizen's behaviours and orientations towards the energy transition

Prof. Dr. Martina Schrautner, Dr. Cleopatra Shikuku, Sabine Lutz

10705 | PORTIA | Fraunhofer | ENEC | Imperial College London | AIMS/ENES | UK

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Goals of WP 2

Gendered intersectional patterns in energy use and access

- WP 2.1 Quantitative study**
Survey across several countries in Europe and Africa with a total case number of 30,000 respondents, distributed across 10 countries, including 6 EU member states and 4 Sub-Saharan African countries (conducted by a service provider)
- WP 2.2 Co-creation**
Depth survey with the expert panel to assess the theoretical understanding of the explored data patterns
- WP 2.3 Case study**
Test the applicability of the theoretical framework in concrete cases of the energy transition through 60 interviews with individuals (conducted by the service provider)
- WP 2.4 Policy advice**
Derivation of policy implications tackling intersectional energy injustices in the energy transition

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Project progress of WP 2

Tender released & questionnaire development in full swing

WP 2.1 08/2023: Task Of: Selection covering & questionnaire preparation

WP 2.1 10/2023: Task Of: Commissioning of initial research: contact with the questionnaire online survey

WP 2.2 01/2024: Task Of: Feedback: Preparation, testing and feedback

WP 2.3 06/2024: Task Of: Data analysis: Regression analysis with identification of intersectional patterns

WP 2.3 06/2024: Task Of: WP 2.3 NA OF: Co-creation with experts

WP 2.4 03/2025: Task Of: WP 2.4 NA OF: Policy implications

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Model assumptions

Exploring identity-related patterns of discrimination in the context of energy consumption and policy

Hypothesis: People experience intersectional patterns of discrimination in the context of their energy consumption and energy policy. The experience of marginalization contribute to a more general self-understanding of being marginalized and powerless.

Control variables: energy use, energy literacy, environmental citizenship, acceptance of green energy, etc.

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Methodological consideration
Once we have the data, we want to explore intersectional patterns in marginalisation in relation to energy use using a MAHDA.

From: Educational Inequalities at the Intersection of Multiple Social Categories: An Introduction and Systematic Review of the Multilevel Analysis of Individual Heterogeneity and Discriminatory Accuracy (MAHDA) Approach

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Opportunities for synergies: free use of the CNEA survey

In the spring to summer of 2023, a series of survey datasets were created in support for the European Climate Infrastructure and Environment (CIE) funding activities and to help to make available to all gEneSys partners to help them manage their work packages. We know the data will be most prepared from and are ready to share if that is of use to you.

Interview schedule (n=2,700)

Conducted between 2018-2020 among 1000+ energy consumers and 1000+ energy providers. Survey topics:

- General energy use (energy bills, energy efficiency, energy security)
- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)
- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)

Energy survey selection of large (L) countries (n=100)

Conducted in 2018-2020 among 1000+ energy consumers and 1000+ energy providers. Survey topics:

- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)
- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)
- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)

Energy survey selection of large (L) countries (n=100)

Conducted in 2018-2020 among 1000+ energy consumers and 1000+ energy providers. Survey topics:

- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)
- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)
- Energy security (energy bills, energy security, energy efficiency, energy security)

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WP3 Development of Concrete Solutions to Advance Women in Energy Transition

Partner: Fraunhofer, ABB, Bosch, Siemens, etc.

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WP3: General description 2

- Duration: 04 – 32M
- Start: 02 PM
- Leading: UI CO leading All partners
- Aims: 1. developing solutions to improve girls' and women's understanding of energy transition jobs and careers panorama as well as their career aspirations and professional involvement in transforming energy landscape from unsustainable to sustainable, 2. promoting gender sensitive education for energy transition.
- Methodology: Theory of change (structured technique for understanding how a programme or set of solutions is likely to contribute to a long-term change).

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WP3 Objectives

- Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among school age students
- Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the traditional and the sustainable, just, and fair energy systems
- Increase participation of women in energy system and transitions as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders
- Promote gender sensitive education for energy transition

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WP3 Tasks

- T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among pre-school and school age students (Months: 6-18)
- T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems (Months: 6-24)
- T3.3 Increase the participation of women in energy systems and in advancing energy transition as researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders (Months: 24-32)
- T3.4 Promote gender sensitive approaches to energy transition in research, innovation and Higher Education (Months: 25-32)

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T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among school age students (Months: 6-18)

- T3.1 will analyse how energy is taught at primary/secondary school and map existing curricula and teaching materials from a gender perspective.
- Based on the findings of the analysis and additional input from related efforts in Physics and Engineering, a guide for intervention will be designed and tested, for teachers and for education policy makers.
- A toolbox will be realized to provide teachers with guidelines for developing their own skill in identifying the signs of unequal gender representation in their textbooks and other materials, then be able to make appropriate changes to their materials or the way in which they use them. Finally, since many teachers may want to create original teaching content, we want to raise awareness to prevent them from unconsciously introducing some sort of gender bias. (Leader: UI CO lead: BBEA, Imperial, IAC)

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T3.2 Analyse and compare female students' attitudes to jobs and careers in the fossil fuel-based vs. the renewable energy systems (Months: 8-24)

- T3.2 responds to the research showing that women are drawn to occupations which are pro-social, creative, collaborative, and inclusive.
- The higher proportion of women in renewables than in fossil fuel energy sectors suggests that women may find jobs in energy systems that are equitable, just, and far more attractive than traditional, male dominated energy sectors. Taking this observation as a departure point T3.2 will use participatory and co-creation approaches involving university students and teachers to provide new insights and practical solutions to help universities review their pedagogies and career advice by paying attention to the values of inclusion, sustainability, justice, and fairness when promoting skills and careers for the *green new deal* professions or jobs and careers. (Leader: LIJ Co-lead: Portia, Imperial, IAC, AIMS)

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WP3 Deliverables & Milestones

Deliverables

- D3.1 – Guidance notes for education policy makers on integrating gender perspective into all levels of education on transitions in energy system (18M, LIJ)
- D3.2 – Policy briefs on intersectional and gender-sensitive energy transformation (30M, LIJ)
- D3.3 – Analyses of and recommendations for training programmes on gender sensitive energy transition (28M, LIJ)
- D3.4 – Toolbox with good practices and new methods in teaching materials and curriculum (30M, Fraunhofer)

Milestones

- Reflexive national workshops (30M, LIJ)
- International masterclasses on pedagogy and training on gender aspects of energy transition (30M, LIJ)

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Partners' involvement in WP3

Participant	T3.1	T3.2	T3.3	T3.4
1. CNR			Leader	Co-lead
2. LIJ	Leader	Leader	Leader	Co-lead
3. ENEA	Co-lead			
4. Fraunhofer	Co-lead	Co-lead	Co-lead	Leader
5. AIMS Rwanda		Co-lead		Co-lead
6. Portia gGmbH		Co-lead		Co-lead
7. Imperial	Co-lead	Co-lead	Co-lead	Co-lead

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T3.1 Improve awareness of and education on sustainability and energy transition among school age students (Months: 6-18)

- T3.1 will analyse how energy is taught at primary/secondary school and map existing curricula and teaching materials from a gender perspective.
- Based on the findings of the analysis and additional input from related efforts in Physics and Engineering, a guide for intervention will be designed and tested, for teachers and for education policy makers.
- A toolbox will be realised to provide teachers with guidelines for developing their own skill in identifying the signs of unequal gender representation in their textbooks and other materials, then be able to make appropriate changes to their materials or the way in which they use them. Finally, since many teachers may want to create original teaching content, we want to raise awareness to prevent them from unconsciously reproducing some sort of gender bias. (Leader: LIJ Co-lead: ENEA, Imperial, IAC)

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Energy in primary and secondary school education curricula

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Diagnosis 10

1000 What are the main objectives, goals, and outcomes of your current intervention?

1000 How are these objectives, goals, and outcomes being achieved?

1000 How are these objectives, goals, and outcomes being achieved?

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Top-down approach

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Diagnosis 11

1000 How are these objectives, goals, and outcomes being achieved?

1000 How are these objectives, goals, and outcomes being achieved?

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or Case studies?

4. Relate to the steering group curricula
3. Understand the context of school teaching programmes
2. Identify textbooks
1. Choose the location and types of school

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Design the factors influencing Gender-Energy nexus

1. Input from SLRF input from GLR

- technologies,
- policies,
- social and individual practices,
- gender gap,
- economic factors

2. Other (like related to the pathways? WP 2)

- values
- goals
- possible career paths
- skills

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Partners' involvement in WP3

Partner	PMs in WP3
1. CNR	8.00
1.1. VIU	
2. IJ	24.00
3. ENEA	8.00
4. Fraunhofer	3.00
5. AIMS Rwanda	5.00
6. Portia gGmbH	3.00
7. Imperial	3.00
Total Person-Months	52.00

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Thank You!

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gEneSys

Transforming Gendered Interrelations of Power and Inequalities in Transition Pathways to Sustainable Energy Systems

WP4 – T4.1 Review the past and still active research and innovation cooperation programmes

Prof Nana Ama Browne Klutse, Institute of Mathematical Sciences (AIMS)

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European Parliament's call for cooperation

- The European Parliament has consistently emphasized the importance of cooperation between the European Union (EU) and Africa across various aspects, including economic development, trade, security, addressing SDGs and climate change.
- **Climate Change and Sustainability:** This includes supporting renewable energy projects, climate adaptation strategies, and conservation efforts.
- **Education and Capacity Building:** Calls for cooperation in education and capacity building are common. These include scholarship programs, vocational training, and initiatives to enhance skills and knowledge transfer.
- **Youth Leadership:** Encourage the development of leadership programs specifically tailored to empower young leaders. These programs can help address the youth demographic challenge in Africa by nurturing future leaders.
- **SDGs:** Calls provide a comprehensive framework for addressing poverty, inequality, environmental sustainability, and other critical issues. Encourage joint efforts to track progress toward SDG targets.
- **Support for Startups and SMEs:** promote, Innovations, Inclusive Entrepreneurship: Advocate for initiatives that support the growth of startups and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Africa. These can include access to funding, mentorship programs, and business incubators.

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European Union-Africa Summits

- These summits have been held periodically over the years, with the most recent taking place in 2022 in Brussels
- Africa-Europe Investment Package of EUR 150 billion that will support a common ambition for 2030 and AU Agenda 2063. Aims to boost public and private investment in:
 - **energy transition** that is fair, just and equitable, taking into account the specific and diverse orientations of the African countries with regards to access to electricity
 - **green transition**, including supporting the implementation of the national plans of African countries under the Paris Agreement
 - **digital transformation** that supports connectivity and affordable and better access to the digital and data economy
 - **sustainable growth and decent job creation**, including by investing in the creation of businesses owned by young people in Africa
 - **transport** facilitation and efficiency of connected transport networks mobility and employability of students, young graduates and skilled workers

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Post-Cotonou Agreement

- EU-OCPS Partnership Agreement
 - The partnership agreement will serve as the new legal framework for EU relations with 79 countries including 47 African
- The agreement aims to strengthen the capacity of the EU and the ACP countries to address global challenges together. It focuses on six priority areas:
 - democracy and human rights
 - sustainable economic growth and development
 - climate change
 - human and social development
 - peace and security
 - migration and mobility

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The Africa-EU Renewable Energy Cooperation Programme (RECP)

- The RECP focuses on meso-scale renewable energy investments, related to all renewable energy resources.
- Meso-scale projects have substantial potential for increasing energy access. The RECP is based on four Action Areas:
 - **Policy Advisory:** Support the development of a policy and regulatory framework favourable to private investment.
 - **Private Sector Cooperation:** Facilitate African and European business cooperation for co-investment, exchange of expertise and technology and promote investment in Africa's renewable energy markets.
 - **Access to Finance:** Support renewable energy projects to reach bankability, assisting viable project ideas to develop into concrete investment opportunities.
 - **Innovation and Skills Development:** Support the development of technical capacities and business skills by creating an African-European network including research, education and private sector institutions.

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UN WOMEN

- **Promoting Access to Clean Energy** - women and marginalized communities have access to clean and affordable energy sources
- **Empowering Women in the Energy Sector:** supports women's active participation in the energy industry.
- **Gender-Responsive Energy Policies:** supports governments and stakeholders to develop and implement gender-responsive energy policies.
- **Energy for Sustainable Development:** align gender equality with sustainable energy development.
- **Data and Research:** research and collects data to better understand the gender dimensions of energy access and energy poverty.
- **Advocacy and Awareness:** awareness about the link between gender, energy, and development.
- **Partnerships:** collaborates with governments, international organizations, non-governmental organizations, and the private sector to promote gender equality in the energy sector. These partnerships facilitate the implementation of gender-responsive energy initiatives.
- **Rural Electrification:** ensures that rural and remote communities, including those often marginalized, have access to electricity and modern energy services.

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Other Programmes and Agreements

- **Horizon Europe** – Many projects funded in the past and present with focus on SDGs
- **Ezemus** - funding programme - social inclusion, the green and digital transitions
- **European Investment Bank (EIB) Financing:** has been providing financing for development projects in Africa for many years, and its activities support action to mitigate climate change
- **UN Sustainable Development Agenda**
- **UNESCO educational initiatives**
- **National research funding mechanisms in Europe for women researchers in Africa**
- **Support mechanisms in Europe that target women innovators and entrepreneurs, etc.**

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Gender Energy Transition nexus

- We get Energy and Energy Transition programmes and agreements
- We have gender and inclusiveness programme and agreements
- Not common to get Gender-Energy Transition programmes
- The gaps will lead us into the next phase
 - Identify the needs and opportunities to advance women in Africa as energy transition researchers, innovators, entrepreneurs, and leaders

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Timeline

- Conclude on the review report by December 2023
- Start needs analysis and opportunities – November 2023

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Thank You !

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- Berth - DGenery, Leap, Gender STI
- Russo – EUECOMAS, EU4U, sustainable energy for All,
- FAO – Energy
- Clemens – cooperation programmes (policy or development)
- Hydro

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gEneSys

WP5 Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions

Berlin, October 24-25, 2023

Dr. Pradi Dhar-Chowdhury, Senior Research Fellow, Centre for Environmental Policy
Dr. Yoon Gwan, Research Associate, Centre for Environmental Policy

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Which criteria would you include for a credible energy transition pathway? You can include up to three

© Start presenting to display the poll results on this slide.

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#2213 949

Which criteria would you include for a credible energy transition pathway? You can include up to three

Learning of CO2 emissions

Gender equality, Renewable energy, Distributive justice, Energy efficiency, Just transition, Resilience impacts, Social cohesion, Inclusiveness, Stability, Energy safety, Just access, Sustainability, Participatory engagement, Air access to energy, Political engagement, Resilient growth, Clean energy, Other goals, Planetary boundaries, Gender just, Does it work with you?

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WP1 results

- Energy Systems Ontology should be viewed as **living entity that** will continuously evolve and expand throughout the project lifecycle, adapting to the requirements of other work packages. For example, it could serve as a valuable tool to support definition of **just energy transition pathways** by leveraging the semantic relationships within the ontology derived from the interdependencies among the different subsystems within the energy domain. It is worth noting that now only a few concepts in the ontology relate to gender.
- Five subsystems: **environment, strategy, policy, behavior and operations.**
- ICL requested to add to the systematic literature review pathways: "to assess the presence of a pathways analysis within the publication"

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Energy transitions pathways

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Energy transition pathways as normative descriptions of how the world could look like over time when realising a common goal (Lau et al., 2020)

Attainment is... a path toward environmentally sustainable and inclusive economies and societies, which promote and defend a set of shared values (IPU, 2021)

High carbon energy production and consumption → Green Low carbon innovations into energy systems (generation and demand) with just, resilient and physical infrastructure → Circular just/Alternative gender & inclusiveness Low carbon provisions into energy systems with just, resilient and physical infrastructure and social/gender equity

Empowering citizens to engage in the transformation to a decarbonised society = **Generative co-creation**

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Uncertainties in NZE and bioenergy

Reduction in total final consumption due to behavioral changes by fuel in the NZE

- Specialise the roles played by bioenergy, carbon capture and behavioural changes
- NZE is a path (not only possibility)
- Technology development
- Global cooperation
- Transition: ensuring the security of fuel and electricity supplies at

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Task 5.2 Integrating gender perspectives into Energy SHIFTS Months 1-12. (Leader: IC, Co-leads: CNRUU, IAO, Imperial, ENEA, Portia)

- Analyse each of the questions recommended by Energy SHIFTS to identify **if it is necessary to add a gender perspective to the topic with a key source of evidence included to validate the decision** (WP1).
- To conduct this assessment TS.2 will apply **the Gendered Innovation approach**.
- The results will contribute to development of "credible" pathways by improving opportunities for social innovation in energy transition processes

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SSH400 questions

Meeting September 4th, 2022 with partners, it was agreed that ICL would test suggestion by Portia (SHIFTS, 2023)

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

Steering Committee

Applying GIA to Theme 1: Transformative Governance

Questions address the aspects of guiding and navigating the fundamental changes from the existing fossil-dominated energy regime to a renewables-based energy system.

- How gender is relevant to governance of a transition to a low-carbon economy [8]
- Conceptualising power in the context of long-term process of structural change [9]
- How gender and intersectional analysis enhance the understanding of power, diversity and justice in sustainability transitions [10][11]
- Social innovation for inclusive and accelerated energy transitions with appropriate governance [12]
- Energy communities, engaging people and technologies in the future of energy [13]
- Assessing the gender and social dimension of energy transition [14]
- Gender inequalities in energy access: How professionals construct and envision gender equity in energy access [15]

1. Rethinking Research Priorities and Outcomes [8]
 2. Rethinking Concepts and Theories [9]
 3. Formulating Research Questions [10, 11]
 4. Analysing Sex [10, 11]
 5. Subverting Gender [10, 11]
 6. Analysing how Sex and Gender Interact [10, 11]
 7. Intersectional Approaches [10, 11]
 8. Engineering Innovation Processes [12]
 9. Co-creation and Participatory Research [13]
 10. Rethinking Standards and Reference Models [14]
 11. Rethinking Language and Visual Representations [15]

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11. What are new economic principles, incentives and institutions needed to support a fair transition towards a just energy system?

12. How can the implications of speed and the implications of social justice and inclusion be reconciled in questions of renewable energy implementation?

13. What is the role of disruptive events as potential game-changers in transitions to renewable energy systems?

14. What is the scope and potential of gendered governance innovations (i.e. citizen-led system enablers) for renewable energy to develop sustainable energy systems and how can they be supported?

15. What are the effective measures of engaging citizens in generating, consuming and distributing energy differently?

16. What are the main challenges and opportunities for the formation of flourishing of renewable energy communities?

17. What are the lessons learnt from the socio-technical energy transitions? R&A

18. How can we employ the full potential of technological and digital innovation processes to create distributed user-friendly, sustainable, accessible and equitable systems of energy production, distribution and use?

19. How is it possible to combine the production of renewables with a reduction in energy demand instead of increasing its endless demand?

20. How can energy governance processes be developed that balance the need for expert knowledge and management of renewable energy (technocracies) on the one hand, and increasing participation and the priority of citizens in energy transitions on the other?

21. Which new forms of alternative governance structures are able to accelerate energy production?

22. How do renewables finance and shape energy transition pathways (e.g. subscription vs. multipoint vs. crowdfunding)?

23. How can renewable energy transitions be facilitated with progress and research policies and discussions?

24. What potential do new organisational forms of energy production, exchange and consumption have for equity or alternative development trajectories in developing countries?

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3. What is the role of disruptive events as potential game-changers in generalised transitions to renewable energy systems?

4. What is the scope and potential of gendered governance innovations (i.e. citizen-led system enablers) for renewable energy to develop sustainable energy systems, and how can they be supported?

5. What are the effective measures of engaging citizens in generating, consuming and distributing energy differently?

6. What are the main challenges and opportunities for the formation of flourishing of renewable energy communities and communities of practice?

7. What are the lessons learnt from the socio-technical energy transitions? R&A

8. How can we employ the full potential of technological and digital innovation processes to create distributed user-friendly, sustainable, accessible and equitable systems of energy production, distribution and use?

9. How is it possible to combine the production of renewables with a reduction in energy demand instead of increasing its endless demand?

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12. How can gender equitable energy governance processes be developed that balance the need for expert knowledge and management of renewable energy (technocracies) on the one hand, and increasing participation and the priority of citizens in energy transitions on the other?

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Applying GIA to Theme 2: Cultural Imaginaries Narratives

Questions explore various cultural aspects of a transition towards a renewables-based energy system, such as the role of socio-technical imaginaries, learning and media discourses.

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12. What are the challenges that transition to renewable energy poses to multi-, inter- and transdisciplinary university education?

13. How do the political contexts of climate emergency affect the unfolding of transitions to renewable energy systems?

14. What are the challenges and opportunities in high population density areas for renewable energy systems?

15. What are the foundations of community regarding renewables? R&A

16. What is the role of diverse socio-imaginaries in regarding the implementation of sustainable energy technologies?

17. What is the influence of counter-narratives on the diffusion of renewables? How are the different imaginaries of the renewables socially constructed and produced in the local world?

18. How are the different imaginaries of the renewables socially constructed and produced in the local world?

19. What are the socio-technical imaginaries of renewables in different regions of the world? In particular, how may they vary across China, India, USA, European countries, and Africa countries?

20. Which renewable energy format is coming?

21. What are the socio-technical imaginaries of renewable future in the countries dependent on energy imported by fossil fuels?

22. What is the role of needs (both traditional and modernities) in facilitating discursive boundary between different social groups around renewable energy solutions?

23. What are the energy practices associated with renewables?

24. What approaches to energy education can facilitate rapid uptake of renewables?

25. How can new renewable energy technologies be distributed in the periphery of territories by their inhabitants?

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Applying GIA to Theme 3: Social Acceptance

Questions address the factors shaping social acceptance for different renewable energy technologies and emphasise aspects of trust-building and citizen empowerment.

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T1

29. Which factors influence the perception of renewables among citizens?
 30. What determines the difference in public acceptance of different gender-equitable renewable energy sources and related infrastructures?
 31. What are the possibilities to transform public opinion and lifestyles, so as gender-equitable renewables would be given preference over other types of energy sources?
 32. What are the gender demographics of renewable energy diffusion and adoption?
 33. What drives the social acceptance and trust of renewable energy technologies and how can local involvement in gender-equitable renewable energy be promoted, as part of ensuring a just transition?
 34. How can the social acceptance in cross-national cooperation for gender-equitable renewable energy in Europe be increased?

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34. How can the social acceptance in cross-national cooperation for renewable energy in Europe be increased?

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Discussion: Proposal to partners and next steps

- Share with partners Excel file with 100 questions for each of the SHFT projects:
 - Renewable Energy
 - Smart Consumption
 - Energy Efficiency
 - Transport (should this be included? Is this needed?)
- Partners identify which questions are suitable for integrating 'gender' using the Gendered Innovation Approach (11 methodologies) and select evidence to validate your choice of GI methodology, evidence (research articles with concrete case studies) is to be selected from papers in literature review database already identified in WP1 for each chosen question
- Need to decide who is going to do what next bearing in mind that these inputs will need to be incorporated into D5.2 Report on Gender Perspectives into Energy Shifts due end of January 2024
- Selected inputs from Task 5.1 and 5.2 will help preliminary identification of some of the pathways

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Timeline for T5.2

- IC to share the 300 questions among partners (by end of the week)
- Partners to carry out the task (applying GIA to the SHFT questions with piece of evidence) by 8th December
- Draft report of D5.2 shared with partners on 15th January
- Submission of final version of D5.2 on 31st January

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Applying the GI methodologies to the 100 Renewable Energy Shifts

1. Renewable Energy Shifts: The analysis... (text continues)

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Applying the GI methodologies to the 100 Renewable Energy Shifts

1. Renewable Energy Shifts: The analysis... (text continues)

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Applying the GI methodologies to the 100 Renewable Energy Shifts

1. Renewable Energy Shifts: The analysis... (text continues)

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

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Cont.

Deliverable ID	Report or deliverable title	Lead	Start	End	Status
Deliverable 5.1.1	Report on shared pathway for gender equality
Deliverable 5.1.2	EU Gendering gender perspectives on ETS recommendations for research, innovation and education
Deliverable 5.1.3	EU Gendering gender perspectives on ETS recommendations for research, innovation and education
Deliverable 5.1.4	EU Gendering gender perspectives on ETS recommendations for research, innovation and education

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- Target activities during March – October 2023
- Identify change actors, stakeholders, and relevant influencers in Europe, Africa and globally, and create a database with an agenda for their engagement
 - Engage key actors/stakeholders/participants directly in the project activities at national and European level, in Africa, and globally
 - Promote science-policy-society dialogue about interrelationships of power
 - Help relevant projects and initiatives in Europe and Africa to apply gender analysis tools and intersectional perspectives to understand the barriers and obstacles to achieving equitable, inclusive, and sustainable outcomes.

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- Identifying and engaging change actors: current status
- Current database includes ~400 actor and stakeholder organisations (covering the six subsystems)
 - 23rd Gender Summit – Africa, Africa's Energy Transition Pathways and Green Deal through the Gender Lens (900 registered participants)
 - European Sustainable Energy Week 2023
 - The 27th International Conference on Science, Technology and Innovation Indicators, 2023
 - LEAPRE Europe-Africa Collaboration on Renewable Energy: 83 partners in ~30 projects
 - Energy Community (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo, North Macedonia, Georgia, Moldova, Montenegro, Serbia and Ukraine)
 - The Association of the European Renewable Research Centers/European Master in Renewable Energy

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- Dialogues involving science, policy & society
- QNEAStudy Workshop, 12 October to validate Foresight results on gender balance in Energy sector in 2050
 - Gender Balance and Power Relations in Energy Transition, QNEAStudy-geneSys joint Webinar 4th December 2023 (Zoom) with presentations from five invited experts on the six core sub-systems in the geneSys energy transition ecosystem model
 - Policy
 - Society-cultures
 - Environment
 - Economy
 - Governance
 - Technology

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- Helping relevant projects and initiatives in Europe and Africa to apply gender analysis tools: current targets
- LEAPRE Europe-Africa Collaboration on Renewable Energy projects, via joint webinars
 - Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions: Co-fund programmes, e.g., Energy for Future (E4F) and Doctoral ITNs, e.g., FLOWNER
 - European Master in Renewable Energy
 - Opportunities through ERASMUS+ projects
 - Opportunities through relevant COST Actions, e.g., Connecting the Energy Research Landscape
 - Opportunities through professional women's network

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

5.4. ANNEX 4: gEneSys KOM power point presentations on preliminary results

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

Glossary

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Taxonomy

10

Semantic Network

11

Ontology

12

Ontology: Some figures

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Conclusions

- Multidisciplinary perspective of the energy system
 - Environment, strategy, policy, human behavior, and energy operations
 - It builds upon the EFO foundational ontology to ensure semantic precision
 - It incorporates a set of 18 ontology design patterns
- Project Goals
 - Common shared language for gEnEsys
 - To facilitate the identification of the energy system knowledge community T1.3
 - To facilitate the identification of the participants who will be engaged in the T1.5 survey
 - To support definition of just energy transition pathways ?

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Thank You !

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Summary/outline of the 2nd steering committee meeting

Glossary

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Thank You !

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